

INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the current problems of using digital technologies in the process of teaching Russian. It considers the main types of digital educational technologies (mobile technologies, virtual reality technologies, gamification and web quest, artificial intelligence) and their application. The inclusion and use of digital tools in the educational process makes it possible to diversify the types of educational activities, increase the effectiveness of learning and the level of motivation for learning Russian.

Keywords: digital technologies, teaching the Russian language, digitalization, digital tools, language learning.

Introduction

One of the trends in modern education is the increasing integration of digital technologies into the educational process. The process of universal digitalization requires the modernization of the modern educational process. In this regard, it is necessary to take a careful approach to the selection of innovative educational technologies and adhere to the principles that allow the most effective implementation of these technologies in the learning process.

The future of modern schoolchildren is inextricably linked with technology. Learning with their help will allow them to quickly adapt and succeed in further studies, careers and adult life. Therefore, the importance of introducing digital devices and applications into school practices is beyond any doubt.

The current stage of methods of teaching Russian is also characterized by the use of a variety of digital technologies. The relevance of the study was determined by such factors as the growing interest on the part of teachers in the possibilities of digital technologies. Advances in technology are used in classroom using digital technologies depending on stage of use, functionality, implementation of linguodidactic tasks, etc.

However, it is difficult for Russian language teachers to navigate modern technologies for a number of reasons: rapid changes in digital technologies, the emergence of new ones, insufficient comprehensive scientific research into the didactic capabilities of various digital technologies in teaching.

Materials and Methods

The purpose of this article is to identify the didactic possibilities and properties of digital technologies in teaching Russian, which will provide students with an engaging learning experience.

Data was collected through theoretical analysis of modern scientific and educational research on the use of digital technologies in teaching Russian; an analytical method for assessing the quality of digital services that can be used in teaching Russian, and generalization by the author of the article of his practical experience in the use of digital technologies for the development of various components of foreign language competence.

Results and discussion

The digital technologies in the educational process can intensify the learning process, improve the quality of education and the effectiveness of training. They help diversify the content, methods and forms of training, stimulate students to independently solve educational problems, and develop independent work skills.

Modern digital services are constantly updated and expanded, so the teacher is faced with the task not only apply all existing digital services, but learn to use the whole variety of digital tools and online services, determining their functionality depending on the desired results [1, p.5].

"Digital technologies are a means by which the issues of intensifying and optimizing education, educating individuals adapted to life in the information society are successfully resolved" [2, p. 9].

The digital educational environment was discussed by such Kazakhstani methodologists and researchers as Chaklikova A.T., Nurgalieva G.K., Dzhusubalieva D.M., Tazhigulova A.I., Artykbaeva E.V., Arystanova A.Zh., Assmatullaeva N.S.

The use of modern digital technologies, which include information, computer, mobile, and network technologies, not only makes it possible to solve one of the main tasks of learning - increasing the level of proficiency in the Russian language, but also significantly contributes to increasing motivation and cognitive activity in the process of learning it thanks to various multimedia and interactive resources.

Digital technologies allow the teacher to adapt the educational process to the individual characteristics of the students [3]. The didactic properties of digital technologies are visualization, interactivity, hypertextuality, multimedia, personalization.

There are the following types of digital technologies:

- digital simulator tasks
- mobile technologies (mobile applications, online services with a set of digital tools)
- cloud technology
- virtual reality technologies
- gamification and web quest
- artificial intelligence.

Examples of digital technologies include educational and didactic platforms such as Mentimetr,

Google Forms, Canva, World Wide Web, Infotest, Kahoot and some others.

Digital technologies make it possible to present material using video, audio and other formats, as well as applications, which contributes to better understanding and retention of lessons. Visualization of material, listening and viewing excerpts of original works of Russian authors can improve the perception of literary works. In addition, the combination of different methods and techniques in the learning process contributes to a deeper disclosure of the topic and retains the attention of schoolchildren.

Now mobile learning technology is most in demand in the field of education. Thanks to its use, the most convenient and productive collaboration and knowledge exchange becomes possible. Smartphones and tablets help teachers trace students' learning and provide more feedback if it is necessary [4].

Teachers and schoolchildren can exchange material remotely, transfer mobile devices within class, using wireless networks, infrared functions of a pocket personal computer.

Cloud technologies have convenient network access, allow you to store a large amount of information and make it possible to use it with minimal management effort, i.e. the cloud allows you to distribute, process and store data.

Gamification allows you to increase schoolchildren's motivation, intensify educational and cognitive activity using a competitive and visualized approach, aimed at solving practical problems of any level of complexity.

Digital technologies have opportunities for creating a variety of interactive tasks. Using the Joyteka service tools, you can create tasks in the form of a webquest. Based on the templates, the teacher enters questions, after which a webquest is automatically created. For example, to open a door in a virtual room, a student needs to find clues and then answer questions correctly. The teacher can create an interactive video in the Joyteka service on a specific topic and upload it [5, p.170].

Virtual reality technologies help schoolchildren interact or immerse in a virtual world using a computer program. Schoolchildren wearing virtual reality glasses or using a PC must make words from morpheme stars, select words with a certain morphemic composition, note changes in lexical meanings when the composition of words changes, etc.

The artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology that is used in solving *intelligent* problems, and all its developments are aimed at creating programs for image recognition, systems.

The main types of software products based on artificial intelligence may include adaptive learning programs, which include new technologies to increase the level of knowledge taking into account the individual characteristics of the student (emotional state, gender, ability to perceive various types of information, level of educational skills). The use of AI in education helps track progress along a student's individual educational trajectory[6].

Artificial intelligence is used in grading, where a computer program imitates the behavior of teachers when checking homework. It can assess schoolchildren's knowledge, analyze responses, provide personalized feedback, and create a training plan tailored to the individual.

Artificial intelligence technologies can be used in the digital "smart campus" technology, when a robot answers student requests related to study and life: how to find a class, register for a chosen course, receive assignments, and contact a teacher.

AI cameras are capable of analyzing student behavior: they can recognize and evaluate reactions to different topics and tasks, which allows teachers to determine the strengths and weaknesses of students.

Conclusion

Analysis of digital technologies has shown wide possibilities for their use in practice of teaching Russian. Digital technologies can be used at the stage of presentation, development and control of phonetic, lexical and grammatical material.

The digital learning materials can be used by teachers as examples and templates to create their own. The digital technologies discussed in the article (digital simulator tasks, mobile technologies, cloud technology, virtual reality technologies, gamification and artificial intelligence) are distinguished by free or shareware access, templates and simple technological solutions for creating original educational content.

Taking into account the selected didactic properties of digital technologies (visualization, interactivity, hypertextuality, multimedia, personalization) will allow optimizing the teaching of Russian. Use of digital technologies can save the teacher's time, increase student engagement and motivation.

Thus the digital technologies can be used to create educational material, interactive tasks, do projects and organize independent work.

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